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Motorhomes as a Housing Alternative for the Indonesian Millennial Generation

Aryo Akbar Aldiansyah¹

¹ Department of Architecture, Universitas Islam Indonesia, Yogyakarta. Indonesia

Correspondence: Aryo Akbar Aldiansyah, S.T., M.Arch., School of Management, Department of Architecture, Universitas Islam Indonesia, Yogyakarta. Indonesia. E-mail: aryo.akbar.aldiansyah@uii.ac.id

Abstract

Motorhomes/campervans are a long-standing fad that is currently making a resurgence in all parts of the world. Because of the versatility of the motorhome, this lifestyle has grown in popularity, not only among hippies, but also among families who wish to have fun or live a nomadic (moving) existence, especially with the rapid rise of the Internet of Things. We can learn from the Covid-19 pandemic that work and study can be done anywhere, whether at home, in recreational spaces, in third rooms, and so on. Motorhomes can now be purchased at reasonable costs. Furthermore, the motorhome can be customized to meet your specific demands and functions. Motorhomes can be created from simple automobiles using any car foundation, such as an MPV, Van, SUV, Middle Size Bus, Full Size Bus, or even a sedan, rather than full size RVs with big proportions and luxurious equipment. The purpose of this study is to define the motorhome/campervan concept and its potential as an alternative housing type. Furthermore, the potential is fairly large for Indonesian millennials, who appear to have a lot of issues on housing ownership mostly because the affordability (economic) aspect and also considering the raising on nomadic and flexible lifestyle. Motorhomes are an excellent option to economical housing since they are mobile, have flexible layouts, and provide a comfortable living space especially for Youth Indonesia's Millennial who's carving for a unique experience.

Keywords: Motorhome, Flexibility, Nomadic, Dwelling, Millennials

1. Introduction

1.1 Motorhome Trends and The Housing Ownership Problem for Young Indonesian

Motorhome is a popular mode of transportation throughout the world. In some countries, a motorhome is also known as a campervan or an RV. Initially, the train Motorhome was established by hippies who had a desire to travel from one location to another. The flexibility of motorhomes has increased the popularity of nomadic living, not only among hippies, but also among other groups that want to expand their horizons or pursue their dreams. Currently, with the advancement of technology, mobile lifestyle activities are becoming more feasible. More specifically, the Internet of Things, in which the internet can collect data and improve nearly every aspect

of human life. If the quality of one's work has become a defining feature of one's lifestyle, this may now be addressed with the addition of a high-speed internet connection. Humans can boost their productivity while traveling by utilizing Big Data (Internet) technology.

We can learn from the previous conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic that work and study can be done wherever, whether at home, in recreation spaces, in third rooms, and so on. This is done to prevent the virus from spreading further by minimizing physical human contact. Work is no longer constrained by location or time as long as goals and objectives can be met and executed successfully. This is how the phrase "Digital Nomads" came about.

Digital Nomads are workers who frequently travel or migrate from one location to another to work or study. They make advantage of the Internet of Things to boost efficiency while working or learning from anywhere. The fundamental idea is to provide for a great deal of flexibility in the work or study process, both in terms of location and time (Karsten, 2022). Working from home (WFH) is a word that is gaining popularity. This benefits not only workers, but also businesses that do not need to provide physical work space in order to save operational costs.

Before delving into the topic of motorhomes, it would be prudent to perform a study of excellent residential standards in terms of various philosophies. Aside from that, an analysis that underpins the requirement for housing can be performed. So that we can comprehend the fundamental nature of residential activities and the fundamental necessities of a residence. This will serve as the foundation for a feasibility study on motorhomes as an alternative housing type for Indonesian Digital Nomads, a trend that is gaining popularity among the millennial generation and younger. As a result, appropriate exploration will be accomplished in efforts to develop this discourse because it fulfills this essence.

1.2 The Housing Ownership Problem for Young Indonesian

It is intriguing to view motorhomes as a new inexpensive typology among Indonesian millennials, since conventional home ownership by the Indonesian millennial generation (born 1976-2001) is now very low. According to PUPR Ministry data from 2019, 81 million Indonesian millennials do not own a home. According to a survey of 3000 respondents, over 41% cited financial concerns as the primary issue.

Figure 1: The Reasons for Young Indonesia to Not Owning a Home Yet

Source: Indonesia Ministry of Public Works, 2019

1.3 The Indonesian Digital Nomads Phenomenon

The Digital Nomads phenomena is spreading throughout the world, including Indonesia. This is exacerbated by the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, which has resulted in severe limits in many aspects of human existence, including work. Work is traditionally done face to face in the workplace, both in the office and in the field, requiring people to physically engage with one another.

However, given to the pandemic's restrictions on physical contact, some organizations have established shifts and modifications in work habits. Fortunately, the internet of things is assisting in the smooth transfer of these

developments. There are numerous options available while surfing the internet without sacrificing work productivity. Meetings can be held virtually, as can collaboration with cloud data systems and a variety of other tasks.

With the spread of the internet of things, numerous previously unknown vocations have gained popularity among people, particularly the younger population in Indonesia. As the primary position, this profession is primarily reliant on internet-based technologies. Social media marketing, retail, bloggers, vloggers, and many more traditional vocations have given way to technology-based ones. Work is no longer constrained by geography or time. Work is becoming increasingly important and results-oriented.

In Indonesia, Bali is a popular tourist destination that is well-planned for digital travelers. This is due to Bali's extensive work infrastructure and recreational facilities. Aside from that, the government has designated Bali as the primary destination for digital nomads, both domestic and international, through work from Bali. Apart from starting a new job, the government wants to rebuild Bali's *gairah*, which is now under construction due to the Covid-19 pandemic. As a result, it is hoped that by having a digital nomad, the general public will benefit from it (Rahayu, 2021).

According to Wiranatha dkk's 2020 study, there are several factors that contribute to Bali's status as a strategic digital node, including (a) Low cost of living, (b) a variety of facilities, (c) the friendliness of the local community, and (d) a variety of weekly or monthly events. Employment and its consequences are prohibited by Executive Order No. 13 of 2003, such as working conditions and usage, are altered. According to several sources, "tenaga kerja" refers to "anyone who can perform work in order to obtain goods and/or services, whether for personal or societal benefit." This definition can be used to categorize Indonesian workers as digital nomads. They usually make money by providing online services (Pradipta 2021).

1.4. The Potent of Motorhome as an alternative dwelling alternative for Indonesia's Millennials

This study's idea is that motorhomes can be an excellent alternative housing type due to its flexibility, low ownership and operating costs. Motorhomes can be built on a variety of platforms, ranging from low-cost cars to high-end vehicles. As a result, this can be tailored to the available budget. Aside from that, RVs provide flexibility in the form of places that can be changed as desired, in keeping with the growing trend of digital nomads, in which the younger generation can live, work, and travel from anywhere, and can be combined with expedition activities.

On the other hand, there will be significant constraints as compared to traditional residential typologies.

2. Method

The purpose of this essay is to investigate the possibility of motorhomes/campervans to become an alternative housing typology that is friendly, affordable, and consistent with the characteristics of Indonesian Millennials. This essay investigates how RVs can serve as a bridge between residential comfort and flexibility and affordability. This paper's hypothesis is that motorhomes can be an alternate housing type for Indonesian Millennials, taking flexibility and financial constraints into account.

The first section is an examination of the function of the motorhome, with a focus on how the housing program can be tailored to the motorhome's limited space, as well as how the motorhome - its user and its surroundings - responds to the program. The normative programs that are often present in conventional residential units are then studied using various theories and then crossed with motorhome capabilities to investigate the possibilities that will be produced. This is done to ensure that the motorhome can work as a compact, comfortable, economical, and versatile dwelling. The conclusion follows next. The final portion will include a discussion of issues that could become research domains in the future.

The majority of the information gathered comes from meta-data approaches. The author attempts to assemble similar data sourced from diverse literary sources before doing data analysis.

Figure 2: The Research Scheme

Source: Writer Analysis

3. Discussion

3.1 Indonesian Motorhome Phenomenon

In recent years, interest in motorhomes/campervans has grown in Indonesia. Learning from the Covid-19 Pandemic is extremely important. With restrictions on human activities that need physical interaction, traveling or living in a campervan has become the primary option. This is also due to changes in the work system, which was formerly restricted by location and time, becoming more flexible. Aside from that, the younger generation in Indonesia values its presence and unique experience, notably the ability to live while moving from one location to another without sacrificing productivity at work. However, motorhome users in Indonesia appear to be dominated by leisure purposes, rather than habitation or residence for a specific period of time.

"For those who want to live in a motorhome/campervan but don't have one, there are currently several campervan suppliers in Indonesia that you can rent from." One well-known example is the Jogja Campervan. There are several tourist destinations to explore, as well as various styles of campervans to rent. In addition to the campervan, renters will receive a tent, mattress, folding chairs, plates, glasses, cutlery, portable stove, and Teflon" (Kumparan, 2022).

The Indonesian Campervan Community (CVI) is one of several Indonesian motorhome communities that discuss and exchange information about the world of motorhomes/campervans. One of the qualities of CamperVan Indonesia (CVI) members is that they do not discriminate between automobile kinds and brands, and everyone is free to adapt his or her vehicle to meet his or her own preferences and needs. Even when indulging in outdoor activities, this community believes that "Home is Where We Park the Car" (Tikum.id, 2021).

3.2 Indonesian Motorhome Affordability

One of the reasons why motorhomes can be a viable alternative housing for young digital nomads in Indonesia is the vehicle's low cost. The type of vehicle can be tailored to your specific requirements and budget. Vehicles that can be used as RVs do not have to be new; they can alternatively be created from good-condition secondhand vehicles. There are numerous sorts of cars on the market, ranging from enormous vehicles with a lot of capacity to small vehicles with limited capacity. The costs of acquiring vehicles also vary substantially, ranging from 30 million to more over 1 billion Rupiah.

According to Carmudi.com, there are a number of low-cost automobile options that can serve as the foundation for a motorhome conversion. These vehicles include the following: (a) Daihatsu Grand Max (60-120 million), (b) Chevrolet Trooper covered (40-90 million), and (c) Hyundai H-1 (150-300 million). Nissan Evalia (60-90 million) (30-50 million) Kia Carnival Suzuki ATV (85-130 million). Aside from that, there are a variety of different vehicles to pick from, such as the Suzuki Hijet, Carry, or VW Combi. Currently, Alphard, Elgrand, Hiace, VW Transporter, and Caravelle are available. Isuzu ELF, Mercedes Benz Vito/ Sprinter, and other large vehicles. It is even possible to turn a regular car into a motorhome with a few alterations.

Figure 3: Left: 4x4 Motorhome. Right: Family Motorhome

Source: Kompas.com

According to an interview with the Managing Director of Karoseri Delima Jaya Group conducted by Kompas Otomotif, the cost of converting a vehicle into a motorhome varies substantially. This is determined by the type of donor vehicle and the required amenities. The cost of a car with a basic minibus ranges between 25 and 55 million rupiah. 125-185 million for a little basic truck. And roughly 300 million rupiah for large-based autos. There are seven feature options that can be adapted to the needs of purchasers, namely: (1). Type of generator (2). (3) split/auxiliary AC. Awnings, either automatic or manual (4). There are five jack stands/car holders. cooking pantry and cooking equipment with gas installation (6). Toilet with pump installation and water tank (7) (shower, toilet, sink, mirror, hanging shelf). Table with adjustable height. [14]

If the changes are made independently rather than through an established body shop, the expenses may be lower. However, the conversion must be carried out carefully and thoroughly through this system so that the results and expenditures incurred are in accordance with the plan. Aside from that, the ability in terms of manufacture and, of course, additional work must be considered in the independent conversion procedure. However, this can be avoided by enlisting the assistance of a carpenter or general mechanic who is not required to specialize in working on RVs.

Laksana carrosserion X Baze's work is one of the conversion works available in Indonesia. The Mahamotorhomes motorhome was constructed from two bases, particularly the Isuzu Targa base (Family type). Meanwhile, the Adventure model is based on a Nissan Navara 4x4 double-cabin truck with improved off-road capabilities, allowing it to reach destinations with more diverse terrain conditions. The conversion process, excluding the vehicle price, is estimated to cost \$300 million.

The low operating costs of a motorhome are one of the factors that entice individuals to live in one. The operational costs incurred vary greatly depending on how frequently you move from one location to another, the distance traveled, the amount of electricity and water used, and the cost of parking or renting a motorhome stop (if any), but most parking is free. The fuel consumption range of the car is 5-15km/l. This fuel factor can be used as a starting point when deciding which automobile to convert.

Figure 4: Delima Jaya Carrosserie Motorhome Prototype

Source: Gridoto.com

A generator can power the motorhome's electrical system. Generator types vary substantially in terms of pricing. The Domestic PGE121 Portable Inverter generator is one example of a generator on the market. This generator costs around 18 million rupiah. This generator, which uses Sine Pure Wave technology, can power laptop computers, refrigerators, electric coolers, and other electronic items in RVs. The PGE121 is suitable for travel

because to its telescoping handle and strong wheels. This generator has 1800 VA of power, has relatively small dimensions of 32 x 43 x 53 cm, and weighs 26.5 kg.

3.3 Normative Dwelling's Program

Housing is an important component of the human life ecology. Life in an ecosystem, according to Estaji (2014), [4] consists of two variables: variables that can be predicted (Fixed) and variables that cannot be predicted. Fixed variables are components of the human life cycle that do not change or vary only slightly. The basic qualities and properties of an object are represented by fixed variables. Meanwhile, the factors do not remain constant (change), necessitating adaptation and flexibility in responding to situations and surroundings. Understanding the fundamental nature of a dwelling is required in terms of housing. What are the citizens' expectations? Housing, on the other hand, must be able to adapt to the current context, both socially, environmentally, culturally, and so on, in order to work properly.

Figure 5: Dwelling System

Source: Edited from Estaji (2014)

A house becomes a setting for its residents' diverse needs and activities. The type of house has an impact not only on human activities within it, but also on the larger ecosystem environment. The dwelling is anticipated to be able to respond to multiple situations at the same time, both within and externally. A house should be able to meet all of its tenants' requirements and desires. In essence, housing can provide a safe and comfortable environment for its people to return home. However, the embodiment and necessity for habitation might be characterized in a complicated way. According to Maslow's Hierarchy of demands hypothesis (1943) [3,] humans have a priority level of demands that must be satisfied first when meeting their needs.

This theory has five degrees of needs. The most basic level is physiological needs, followed by the need for security, followed by the need for love and belonging, followed by the need for esteem, and finally by the need for self-actualization. The most fundamental level is an inherent necessity for every human being. Meanwhile, the drive to actualize oneself and demonstrate one's existence is at the highest level.

Figure 6: The Hierarchy of Dwelling Based on The Maslow's Hierarchy

Source: Edited from Estaji (2014)

According to the preceding hierarchy, a physical dwelling is a shelter that provides and accommodates different basic human needs. Housing, according to ideal standards, is not only a place for refuge and activity, but it is

also an item that may assist its people in maximizing their personal potential. Estaji, 2014 [4]. Several elements, such as environmental aspects (how inhabitants interact with their surroundings), cultural conditions, trends, and so on, will continue to evolve in order to maximize a user's personal potential. In this scenario, there has been a shift in perceptions about the concept of a dwelling, particularly among Indonesian millennial digital nomads. Permanent home ownership is hampered by a variety of factors, including a lack of cash, land, and the millennial generation's attitude toward housing. This is what is fascinating to investigate: how housing building may address these issues and challenges.

According to Hillier's (1984) theory of space syntax, the concept of space may be divided into two categories: space as a background for an activity and space as an inherent part of it, notably moving through space, interacting with other persons in space, and seeing space from a point in it. The second is that human space is not about a single area, but about the interactions of numerous spaces that comprise a whole system. Hillier refers to this as "spatial configuration." Estaji (2014). [4] According to the foregoing theory, space is not only the background for an action, but it is also an essential thing that merges with an activity. Space is therefore characterized not only by its own scope, but also by the connectivity of that space with other spaces in a system. As a result, the notion of space becomes quite varied and flexible in terms of adjusting and responding to context.

4. Discussion

Motorhomes can virtually fulfill all areas of Maslow's theory of human wants, although their coverage is selective rather than comprehensive. Motohome is not capable of meeting all requirements at any rating level. A motorhome can serve as a shelter on the first level (physiological needs). At this level, the motorhome meets the occupants' basic necessities. At the second level, RVs can also meet some safety requirements, albeit they have significant drawbacks when compared to permanent houses. Motorhomes can also meet the livability aspect criteria at the third level. Motorhomes will be able to boost usability and creative use of space in this regard. So that the residents can make the best use of the existing areas. Motorhomes, on the next level, not only provide basic housing demands, but also provide a pleasant (unique) living experience. In the last stage, RV occupants might actualize themselves and demonstrate their existence by delivering a pleasant experience for the tenants.

Figure 7: Motorhome on The Dwelling Hierarchy

Source: Writers analysis

Motorhomes are another sustainable dwelling option. From an environmental standpoint, motorhomes have a negligible influence on the land. This aligns with Glenn Murcutt's architectural manifesto "Touch the Earth Lightly." This allows for a reduction in the negative impact that motorhomes have on the environment. A house must meet certain basic characteristics in order to support the comfort and daily activities of its residents. When it comes to the size and minimal space available in a motorhome, digital nomads who want to live nomadically in a motorhome must make adaptations (downsizing). This is owing to the vehicle's limited room. This must be solved by comprehending the significance of daily activities at home.

Small spaces in the car interior must be structured or built in such a way that they may satisfy the occupants' diverse needs. When the vehicle is halted, extension scenarios can be added to the vehicle's outer perimeter. Another item to consider is the utilization of built-in and retractable furniture. It is believed that with careful planning and design, a mobile living experience may be built that can meet basic life necessities while also providing unique comfort and experiences.

Further research would be fascinating to observe how motorhomes are not only utilized as temporary houses that move from one region to another, but can also offer an alternative for living in a certain spot for a longer amount of time, whether monthly or yearly. This is done, of course, by taking into account and examining the land acquisition strategy, whether on a lease or ownership basis, with a specific scheme.

Author Contributions: the author is expected to have made substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data; or the creation of new software used in the work; or have drafted the work or substantively revised it; AND agrees to be personally accountable for the author's own contributions and for ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work, even ones in which the author was not personally involved, are appropriately investigated, resolved, and documented in the literature.

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